

IDENTIFICATION OF MANGROVES AND THEIR ASSOCIATES IN MANGROVE FOREST AT PICHAVARAM

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ABSTRACT

In the present work an attempt was made to survey of the pichavaram mangrove forest in Tamil nadu have been recorded. A variety of mangrove species and their associated species. The survey has help to identified the dominant species, as well as the threat to the forest

Key words: Mangrove species, Identification and recorded

INTRODUCTION

Pichavaram mangrove forest is one of the largest mangrove ecosystem in India, covering about 45 km² of area located in between the predominant estuaries of the velar and coleroon rivers(Martha rojas urrego,2024)Mangrove are salt tolerant evergreen forest ecosystem found mainly in the tropical and subtropical inter-tidal regions of the world between approximately 32° N and 38° S latitude and total mangrove cover has been estimated to be approximately 15.6 million hectares globally (FAO, 2010). Mangroves are ecologically important components of the coastal ecosystems that are under severe threat globally from a range of causes (Hai et al., 2020) and they provide potential contributions in ecological services (Kumari et al., 2020), provides habitat for many terrestrial and marine species (Nagelkerken et al., 2008), various food resources, shelter and site for fertilization for variety of aquatic fauna resulting into rich biodiversity. These are important to mankind not only as valuable food, but also largely contribute to the maintenance of marine food chain and livelihood. Mangroves help in maintaining the marine ecosystem structure and function through trophic relationship Mangroves

distribution and abundance in intertidal areas could be considered as a direct indicator of the habitat health of the coastal ecosystem and they are highly sensitive to environmental change. In terms of flor diversity total 46 true mangrove species belonging to 14 families and 22 genera are found in Indian mangrove habitats (Ragavan et al., 2016). Around 3 % of the earth total mangrove vegetation are stands in India (FSI, 2019). The Eco physiological studies of mangrove plants that are adapted to various extreme environmental conditions like salinity, high temperatures, low oxygen and contaminated environments are prerequisite to tackle the current problems facing mankind like food security, pollution and the endangered habitats. Mangrove wetlands are characterized by such qualities as a humid climate, saline environment, water logged soil or muddy soil. Mangrove plants grow in waterlogged soils and capable of tolerating salinity ranging from 2% to 90% (Selvam and Karunagaran, 2004). Studies on the ecology, distribution, diversity of mangrove species and mangrove associates have been carried out in many coastal areas in India such as Andhra Pradesh (Madhu sudhana Rao et al., 2015), Andaman and Nicobar CAM Mangroves are among the most productive coastal ecosystems in the world (Kathiresan et al., 2001). Mangrove habitats of India have been facing tremendous threats due to indiscriminate exploitation of mangrove resources for multiple uses like fodder, fuel wood, timber for building material, alcohol, paper, charcoal and medicine (Anand et al 2020, Maurya et al., 2021).

The Pichavaram mangrove forest covers an area of about 1100 ha, of which 50% is covered by forest, 40% by water-ways and the remaining filled by sand-flats and mud-flats (Krishnamurthy and Prince Jayaseelan, 1983). The Pichavaram mangrove is influenced by mixing of three types of waters: 1. Neritic or coastal water from the adjacent Bay of Bengal through a mouth called 'Chinnavaikkal', 2. brackish water from the Vellar and Coleroon estuaries and, 3. fresh water from an irrigation channel (Khan Sahib canal'), as well as from the main channel of the Coleroon river. The year for convenience is arranged into four seasons: 1. post monsoon: January–March; 2. summer: April–June; 3. pre-monsoon: July–September; and, 4. Monsoon (northeast monsoon): October–December. The tides are semi-diurnal and vary in amplitude from about 15 to 100cm in different regions during different seasons, reaching a maximum during monsoon and post-monsoon and a minimum during summer (Muniyandi, 1986). The rise and fall of the tidal waters is through a direct connection with the sea at the Chinnavaikkal mouth and also through the two adjacent estuaries. The depth of the water – ways ranges

from about 0.3 – 3 m (Muniyandi, 1986). The present study aimed to survey the mangroves and their associates present in three different areas of the Pichavaram Mangrove forest.

MATERIALS AND METHODS-

Study area:

Pichavaram mangrove forest (Lat. 11.20N; Long. 79,470 E) is located between the Vellar and Coleroon estuaries, near Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu. The forest occurs on 51 islets, ranging in size from 1100Ha separated by intricate waterways, which connect the Vellar and Coleroon estuaries. The southern part near the Coleroon estuary is predominantly mangrove vegetation, while the northern part near the Vellar estuary is dominated by mud-flats. The Vellar estuary opens into the Bay of Bengal at Parangipettai and links with the Coleroon River, which is distributaries to the River

Species identification

The mangrove vegetation in all the sites under study, scanned by repeated visits in different seasons of the years. The specimens of mangrove plant and associated flora collected from all sites were critically identified to species level with the help of standard books and manuals of mangroves (Banerjee et al., 1989; Naskar, 2004; Pandey and Pandey, 2010), standard field guide to mangroves (Lovelock, 1993), standard literatures (Blasco, 1975; George, 2005; Kathiresan, 2000) and also consulting the flora of madras presidency (Gamble, 1915-1936) for analyzing taxonomically and later verified in the laboratory. And moreover, the herbarium specimen was also verified by the scientists at Gujarat Ecological and Research (GEER) Foundation.

Data collection and duration:

The present study carried out in mangrove and mangrove associated vegetation exists in Killai, T.S.Pettai and Pichavaram were first identified and documented. For the assessment of present biodiversity status, the mangroves, mangrove associated vegetation's existing around the study area were considered for identification. Regular surveys were made throughout the forest to explore the successful results of the true mangroves and their associates. The mangroves and mangrove associated vegetation were plucked during their flowering and fruiting seasons for identification and took

photographs with the help of camera. Thenomenclature of the specimens followed Gamble (1957) and Matthew (1983). Plant specimens were collected whenever identification was not possible in the field. The collected specimens were identified with the help of the publications (Rajendran and BaskarSanjeevi, 2004; Ramanathan, 1997). Nomenclatures of the identifiedspecies were checked with the International Plant Naming Index (IPNI).

RESULT:

Mangrove vegetation divided into two groups such as true mangroves and mangrove associates. Among them, 25 species were recorded in the study period including 12 mangroves and 13 mangrove associated plants. Totally 12 species of mangroves belonging to 9 genera and 7 families were recorded (Table 1). *Avicennia marina*, *Avicennia officinalis* belongs to *Avicenniaceae* and *Rhizophora apiculata*, *Rhizophora mucronata* belongs to *Rhizophoraceae* was most dominant mangrove plant species in Pichavaram mangrove forest. In Pichavaram as well as T.S. Pettai *Avicennia marina*, *Avicennia officinalis* and *Rhizophora mucronata* was most dominant compared to Killai. In T.S. Pettai *Aegiceras corniculatum*, *Bruguiera cylindrica* and *Lumnitzera racemosa* was most dominant species compared to Pichavaram and Killai. *Xylocarpus mekongensis* is an endangered species and it was recorded in few numbers in Pichavaram. Totally 12 species of mangroves associates belonging to 12 genera and 13 families were recorded in Pichavaram Mangrove forest. Six associates *Suaedamaritima*, *Suaedamonoica*, *Ipomoea pes-caprae* and *Sesuvium portulacastrum* were observed as dominant species.

Table 1: Distribution of Mangroves and their families

S.NO	FAMILY	GENEUS	SPECIES
1	Acanthaceae	<i>Acanthus</i>	<i>ilicifolius</i>
2	Avicenniaceae	<i>Avicennia</i>	<i>marina</i>
3	Avicenniaceae	<i>Avicennia</i>	<i>officinalis</i>
4	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Bruguiera</i>	<i>cylindrica</i>
5	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Bruguiera</i>	<i>conjugata</i>
6	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Ceriops</i>	<i>Roxburghiana</i>
7	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Ceriops</i>	<i>decandra</i>
8	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Rhizophora</i>	<i>apiculata</i>

9	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Rhizophora</i>	<i>mucronata</i>
10	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Rhizophora</i>	<i>annamalayana</i>
11	Myrsinaceae	<i>Aegiceras</i>	<i>corniculatum</i>
12	Combretaceae	<i>Lumnitzera</i>	<i>racemosa</i>
13	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Excoecaria</i>	<i>agallocha</i>
14	Meliaceae	<i>Xylocarpus</i>	<i>mekongensis</i>
TOTAL	7	9	14

Table 2: Distribution of Mangrove Associates and their families

S.NO.	FAMILY	GENUS	SPECIES
1	Chenopodiaceae	<i>Arthrocnemum</i>	<i>indicum</i>
2.	Convolvulaceae	<i>cressa</i>	<i>cretica</i>
3	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Citrullus</i>	<i>colocynthis</i>
4	Verbenaceae	<i>Clerodendrum</i>	<i>inerme</i>
5	Fabacea	<i>Derris</i>	<i>trifoliata</i>
6	Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea</i>	<i>pes-caprae</i>
7	Fabaceae	<i>Pongamia</i>	<i>pinnata</i>
8	Chenopodiaceae	<i>Salicornia</i>	<i>brachiata</i>
9	Aizoaceae	<i>Suvium</i>	<i>portulacastrum</i>
10	Poaceae	<i>Spinifex</i>	<i>littoreus</i>
11	Amaranthaceae	<i>Suaeda</i>	<i>maritima</i>
12	Amaranthaceae	<i>Suaeda</i>	<i>monoica</i>
13	Binaceae	<i>Heliotropium</i>	<i>curassavicum</i>
TOTAL:	12	12	13

DISCUSSION

Mangroves play a crucial role in coastal production by mitigating erosion and serving as a nursery for marine life, (Hespen et al 2023, montgomery et al 2022) A total 39 mangroves species were identified from India (Kathiresan, 1999). Tomlinson (1986) reported 60 species mangrove associates belonging to 46 genera and 27 families that exist in the world mangroves. Along the east coast, the least

number of mangrove species is present in Tamil Nadu (Deshmukhand Mahalingam, 1991). Our present study indicated that 14 Mangrove species and 13 associated species were present. Analysis of the distribution of true mangrove species in different areas of Pichavaram Mangroves wetlands indicates that *Acanthus ilicifolius*, *Aegiceras corniculatum*, *Avicennia marina*, *Bruguiera cylindrica*, *Ceriops deandra*, *Excoecaria agallocha*, *Lumnitzera racemosa*, *Rhizophora apicuata*, *Avicennia marina* are common to all the mangroves of Tamil Nadu. The Pichavaram is also characterized by the presence of a natural hybrid of *Rhizophora* species *Rhizophora annamalayana*. *Xylocarpus mekongensis* was also reported in Pichavaram by Kathiresan (2003).

The distribution of mangrove ecosystem on Indian coastlines indicates that the Sundarban mangroves occupy very large area followed by Andaman-Nicobar Islands, Gulf of Kachch in Gujarat and so on including Pichavaram Mangroves in Tamil Nadu. Recent data available from State of Forest Report 2011 of the Forest Survey of India, Dehra Dun shows that mangrove cover in the country is 4,662.56 sq. km, which is 0.14 percent of the country's total geographical area. The threats to the mangrove ecosystem could be broadly grouped into Natural and Anthropogenic. These factors may affect the system as a whole or any one entity within the system. The natural threats include: Climatic changes, Cyclones and Physical processes. Diseases, deterioration, pollution, grazing, agriculture, aquaculture, human encroachment and tsunami (including reclamation), etc., are considered as the anthropogenic threats to the ecosystem (Menendez et al 2021), In the recent years Pichavaram mangrove Region encounters lots of problems such as anthropogenic, grazing, human encroachment, etc. which leads to deterioration in the ecosystem. Government and other Nongovernmental Agencies are vehemently working towards the development in the region. This study has been carried out to assess the present situation to identify the changes took place over a period of time with the help of satellite remote sensing and GIS. Research methods based on satellite data are timesaving, cost-effective and enhance the possibility of classifying the vegetation through spectral and texture analyses; on the other hand, ground measurement methods are difficult, expensive, time-consuming and labor-intensive. The outcome of the study reveals that some parts are degraded and some parts are having increase in mangroves cover and found that overall development has taken place in the mangrove forest. It is suggested that continuous monitoring and development of mangroves region has to be carried out for further improvement. Globally, mangroves are disappearing under the increased threat of human intervention and large scale coastal land reclamation. It is estimated that with the present rate of loss,

ecosystem services of mangroves are likely to be completely lost within the next 100 years. Although, legislative conservation practices are already in place in many countries, particularly, in South and Southeast Asia, this has proved to be insufficient (Das Gupta et al 2013a; 2013b). As an alternative management, community based approaches are evolving, yet, the effectiveness of these approaches are often contested. Recurrent cyclonic storms, over grazing and high soil-salinity resulted considerable fragmentation and degradation of Pichavaram mangroves. Consequently, it affected the local fishing communities; firstly, with a reduction in fish catches and secondly with an increased vulnerability to cyclonic hazards. Particularly, the regeneration of mangroves proved extremely relevant during the Indian Ocean Tsunami in 2004, as strong evidences of its protective role has been well-documented by number of researchers (Kathiresan et al. 2005).

SUMMARY

The mangrove *A. marina* is the dominant species in the intertidal area of all study sites. Mangroves are the best bio indicator of environmental pollution and health of the coastal ecosystem. However they are being threatened by anthropogenic activities like deforestation, soil and water pollution. They need to be conserved and protected for the conservation of genetically divers group of terrestrial and aquatic organisms. In addition, it is suggested that more study should be conducted in this area in the future. The understanding of the structural characteristics of mangrove vegetation is very useful for the future mangrove management and conservation strategies. Development and maintenance of mangrove belt in and around the intertidal area of pichavaram were also suggested, and moreover the continued ecological assessment of mangrove is recommended.

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